

OPPORTUNITIES OF INDUSTRY 4.0 IN TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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Abstract

Purpose – *The research aims to find solutions to implement the concept of circular economy in the textile industry, which is responsible for large amounts of waste, greenhouse gas emissions and land-fill.*

Methodology/approach – *A large number of documents regarding the environmental impact were studied and official decisions issued at European level were considered in order to identify the existing guidelines for reducing waste in textile industry.*

Findings - *The tasks for the textile industry address to new technologies and new materials. The changes are possible by implementing the components of Industry 4.0, including digitization and automation at all stages of the process, beginning with the design of the patterns and ending with packing of final pieces of cloth. Once the needs of this industry are identified, one must find the opportunities among Industry 4.0 components.*

Research limitations/implications – *The results of this research should be detailed for the various activities involved in textile industry.*

Practical implications – *Both companies and education institutions may use the ideas proposed.*

Originality/value – *The present text is a start point for practical implementation.*

Key words: *textile industry, circular economy, Industry 4.0.*

Introduction

It is common knowledge that in the present, the mankind produces huge amounts of waste. The European Union alone is responsible for more than 2.5 billion tones. We all agree that the actual technologies and habits of consumers should change. However, this is not at all a simple task. The technologies working today provide useful products, but drain the natural resources, consume large amounts of energy and water and generate more or less waste harmful from ecological point of view.

Conceptually, the world functions on the linear model of economy (Fig. 1), which is based on a take-make-consume-throw away pattern. This model relies on large quantities of cheap, easily accessible materials and energy. (“Economia circulară: definiție, importanță și beneficii | Actualitate | Parlamentul European”)

The circular economy is a model of production and consumption, which involves sharing, leasing, reusing, repairing, refurbishing and recycling existing materials and products as long as possible (Fig. 2). In this way, the life cycle of products is extended. In practice, it implies reducing waste to a minimum. (“Economia circulară: definiție, importanță și beneficii | Actualitate | Parlamentul European”)

Fig. 1. Linear pattern of economy (“From a Linear to a Circular Economy | Circular Economy | Government.NI”)

Fig. 2. Circular pattern of economy (“Economia circulară: definiție, importanță și beneficii | Actualitate | Parlamentul European”)

In March 2020, the European Commission presented, under the European Green Deal the new circular economy action plan that includes proposals on more sustainable product design, reducing waste and empowering consumers (such as a right to repair). In February 2021, the European Parliament adopted a resolution on the new circular economy action plan demanding additional measures to achieve a carbon-neutral, environmentally sustainable, toxic-free and fully circular economy by 2050.

The most amounts of waste result from sectors such as electronics, plastics, textiles and construction.

Industry 4.0 in Europe, known as Smart Manufacturing in America, Made in China 2025 in China and Innovation 25 in Japan, represents the current trend of automation technologies in the manufacturing industry, and it mainly includes enabling technologies such as the cyber-physical systems (CPS), Internet of Things (IoT) and cloud computing. (Hermann, Pentek, and Otto, 2016; Jasperneite, 2012; Kagermann, Wahlster, and Helbig, 2013)

Industry 4.0 is regarded as the fourth industrial revolution (Fig. 3). (Wright, 2018) It follows the First Industrial Revolution (1760 – 1840) - mechanization through water and steam power, the Second Industrial Revolution (1870 to 1914) - electricity replaced water and steam, started the deployment of assembly lines, interchangeable parts and, mass production and the Third Industrial Revolution (1960 to 20??) – deployment of Robots, CNCs, Computers and Automation.

As an extension of Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0 was defined in order to add a human or social dimension to the technological one. Industry 5.0 places the wellbeing of the worker at the center of the production process and uses new technologies to provide prosperity beyond jobs and growth while respecting the production limits of the planet. It complements the existing "Industry 4.0" approach by specifically putting research and innovation at the service of the transition to a sustainable, human-centric and resilient European industry. (“Industry 5.0 | European Commission”)

Fig. 3. Symbolic representation of the four industrial revolutions (Hermann, Pentek, and Otto, 2016)

The main components of Industry 4.0 are briefly described below:

- Large-scale digitization, which is the base of any other component
- Cyber-physical systems (Fig. 4), which are characterized by a physical asset, such as a machine, and its digital twin (basically a software model that mimics the behavior of the physical asset). (Bagheri, 2015)

Fig. 4. Model of CPS (Bagheri, 2015)

- The Internet of Things (IoT), which is a system of interrelated computing devices, mechanical and digital machines provided with unique identifiers (UIDs) and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to-computer interaction (Fig. 5). (Crimm, 2019)

Fig. 5. Multiple connections suggesting IoT (Crimm, 2019)

- Cloud computing which assumes that most of the user will have the applications and databases on the cloud. Individual desktops and laptops will need smaller power and will work at higher speed (Fig. 6). (Wright, 2018)
- Additive Manufacturing, which has a huge potential to replace the traditional machining technologies. With proper materials and software, freeform pieces with precise dimensions and adequate surface texture can be grown in short manufacturing time. A large range of processes are already in use (power bed fusion, direct energy deposition, binder jetting, material extrusion etc.) and manufacture pieces made of la large variety of materials (metals, thermoplastics, biomedical, ceramics). (“What Is Additive Manufacturing | GE Additive”)

Fig. 6. Diagram of cloud computing system (Wright, 2018)

Environmental impact of textile industry

During the last decades, the textile industry responded to consumer's requirements, namely new styles and low prices. This trend resulted in a very large volume of cloths and household textiles.

The manufacturing of fibers, different fabrics and clothing pollute water, spread greenhouse gas and cause landfill.

Documents issued at the European level provide the following data regarding the actual textile industry ("The Impact of Textile Production and Waste on the Environment (Infographic) | News | European Parliament"):

- 80 billion cubic meters of water are used yearly by the textile and clothing industry (from approx. 270 billion cubic meters consumed by the whole economy)
- 0.5 million tons of microfibers are spilled into the ocean yearly (resulted from washing of synthetic materials)
- 20% of the ocean pollution is due to dyes from textiles
- 10% of global greenhouse gas emissions comes from textile industry (~654 kg of CO2 emission per person in 2017 in Europe)
- Europeans use nearly 26 kilos of textiles and discard about 11 kilos of them every year. Used clothes are mostly (87%) incinerated or landfilled.

An important element in pollution is the dye, beginning with its synthesis and ending with its presence in clothing or household textiles. Numerous studies are dedicated to identifying the effects of dyes and then to the possibilities to find ecofriendly ways of coloring. (Khattab, Abdelrahman, Rehan, 2020; Elshahida, Fauzi, Sailah, Siregar, 2020)

The short statistics above show the need to re-think the whole process of providing textile pieces, in all stages, from the design to packaging.

The changes are possible by means of implementing tool offered by the new concept of Industry 4.0.

Elements of Industry 4.0 suited to be implemented in textile industry

Considering the goal of minimizing waste, pollution and energy or water consumption, the textile industry may follow two directions:

- To continue to use the existing fabric, in terms of fiber nature, shape and dimensions of semi-finished rolls, tailoring and sewing
- To use new materials, which allow the implementation of new technologies.

Figure 7 synthesizes some ideas regarding the possibilities to make textile industry sustainable, in case it continues to use traditional fabric.

Fig. 7. Possible changes in textile industry keeping traditional fabric in use

The opportunities for changes are found among Industry 4.0 components. In cloths manufacturing, for instance, all stages in the process may be altered and improved:

Advanced software and proper algorithms can be developed to generate digital patterns and provide an optimized arrangement of pattens over the surface of fabric so that the waist of fabric to be minimized.

- Cutting of parts should find a solution to reduce the amount of lint which is generated and spread into the atmosphere.
- Manual labor may be replaced by automated or partially automated sewing of parts.
- All working spaces may be controlled regarding the lint amount through intelligent solutions.
- Packages may be designed using ecofriendly or reusable materials.
- The fashion designers may contribute creating fashion trends based on minimalist pieces.

The implementation of the ideas above requires big investments, as for any other smart factory or even more because, at present, the automation in this industry is lower than in technical products manufacturing.

Considering the present fast progress in materials, it is reasonable to think the textile industry will also benefit of this progress. In this case the technology of 3D printing will successfully be applied in this industry too (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Possible changes in textile industry with new materials

Printable materials for manufacturing cloths would bring plenty of benefits, such as:

- Single 3D pattern for a piece of clothing
- Stages of tailoring and sewing eliminated
- High degree of reproducibility
- Shorter machining time
- No manual labor
- Digital command
- Minimum waste

3D printed cloths already appeared, but not yet on industrial scale (“3D Printed Clothes in 2021: What Are the Best Projects?”).

The close future will also bring smart textiles, which can change color, shape or thermal properties as automatic reaction to external stimuli. (Orzan, Zara, Florescu, Orzan, 2020)

Conclusions

The textile industry as one of the most important polluters must find ways to reduce waste, gas emissions and landfill.

However, the changes must take into account several specific features of this industry. Its actual functioning uses very few automated equipment, because the number of identical products is small, the models depending on the season and fashion trend. The producers do not invest in automation for small volume production. They prefer to use cheap manual labor, usually developed in the third world countries. The productivity is very low, but the final small price of the products is convenient both for the producers and the customers.

Technological innovation is the solution to increase productivity, reduce waste and develop green production. The components of Industry 4.0 provide opportunities to be implemented in all stages of manufacturing textile pieces.

Still, the problem as a whole must be addressed from technological, economical and social point of view.

The developed countries in Europe and Northern America, within the present geopolitical and economical context, started to re-evaluate the basic problems, which generated the concepts of

circular industry and Industry 4.0. Natural resources and primary energy became so important, that they will probably guide the research directions in the near future. The solutions will have to be implemented in all economical fields, including textile production.

References

“Economia Circulară: Definiție, Importanță Și Beneficii | Actualitate | Parlamentul European”

Economia circulară: definiție, importanță și beneficii

2018

www.europarl.europa.eu, 4 Oct. 2018,

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/ro/headlines/economy/20151201STO05603/economia-circulara-definitie-importanta-si-beneficii>.

“From a Linear to a Circular Economy | Circular Economy | Government.NI.”

From a Linear to a Circular Economy

2022

<https://www.government.nl/topics/circular-economy/from-a-linear-to-a-circular-economy>. Accessed 8 Aug. 2022.

Hermann, M., T. Pentek, and B. Otto

2016

“Design Principles for Industry 4.0 Scenarios.” In Proceedings of 2016 49th Hawaii International Conference on Systems Science, January 5–8, Maui, Hawaii.

Jasperneite, J.

2012

“Was Hinter Begriffen Wie Industrie 4.0 Steckt.” *Computer & Automation* 12: 24–28. Jia, X., O. Feng, T. Fan, and Q. Lei. 2012. “RFID Technology and its Applications in Internet of Things (IoT).” In Proceedings of the 2nd IEEE International Conference on Consumer Electronics, Communications and Networks (CECNet), April 21–23, Yichang, China: 1282–1285

Kagermann, H., W. Wahlster, and J. Helbig

2013

“Recommendations for Implementing the Strategic Initiative Industry 4.0: Final Report of the Industry 4.0 Working Group.” Acatech-National Academy of Science and Engineering, Germany

Wright, I.

2018

What Is Industry 4.0, Anyway?

<https://www.engineering.com/AdvancedManufacturing/ArticleID/16521/What-Is-Industry-40-Anyway.aspx>

“Industry 5.0 | European Commission.”

2020

European Commission - European Commission, What is Industry 5.0? ec.europa.eu, 1 Nov. 2020, https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/industry-50_en.

Bagheri, B.

2015

Big future for cyber-physical manufacturing systems

<https://www.designworldonline.com/big-future-for-cyber-physical-manufacturing-systems>

Crimm, P., and @TechRadar

2019

“Industry 4.0: For Smarter Operations | TechRadar.” TechRadar, www.techradar.com, 24 July 2019, <https://www.techradar.com/news/industry-40-for-smarter-operations>.

“What Is Additive Manufacturing | GE Additive.”

2022

What Is Additive Manufacturing | GE Additive, www.ge.com, <https://www.ge.com/additive/additive-manufacturing>. Accessed 8 Jul. 2022.

“The Impact of Textile Production and Waste on the Environment (Infographic) | News | European Parliament.”

The Impact of Textile Production and Waste on the Environment (Infographic) | News | European Parliament, www.europarl.europa.eu, 26 Apr. 2022,

<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/headlines/society/20201208STO93327/the-impact-of-textile-production-and-waste-on-the-environment-infographic>.

Khattab, T.A., Abdelrahman, M.S., Rehan, M.

2020

"Textile dyeing industry: environmental impacts and remediation". Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 27(4): 3803-3818

Elsahida, K., Fauzi, A.M., Sailah, I., Siregar, I. Z.

2020

"Sustainable production of natural textile dyes industry". International Conference On Innovation In Technology And Management For Sustainable Agroindustry (ITAMSA 2019). 472: Art. 012036

"3D Printed Clothes in 2021: What Are the Best Projects?"

2021

Sculpteo, www.sculpteo.com, <https://www.sculpteo.com/en/3d-learning-hub/applications-of-3d-printing/3d-printed-clothes>. Accessed 19 Jun. 2022.

Orzan, CM., Zara, IA., Florescu, MS., Orzan, OA.

2020

"Smart textiles perspective for the Romanian fashion industry". Industria textila. 71(6): 572-575